

Dynamic and Scaling Effects in Impact of Composite Structures

Stephen R. Swanson
Department of Mechanical Engineering
University of Utah
Salt Lake City, UT 84112 USA

ABSTRACT

The problem of damage formation and subsequent loss of stiffness and strength resulting from accidental impact in fiber composite structures remains of much concern. The present paper gives the results of a recent investigation of impact of both plates and cylinders, with particular emphasis on dynamic effects and scaling with respect to size. Dynamic analysis procedures were developed for both plates and cylinders. Experiments were carried out with both drop-weight and airgun impact apparatus, using a range of sizes of the plates and cylinders. Rules have been developed so that it is possible to determine whether or not a dynamic analysis is necessary, knowing only the quasi-static deformation for the structure under impact. The scaling effects with respect to specimen size are found to be well understood with respect to deformation, but more complex with respect to damage formation. It is found that both delamination initiation and subsequent propagation are governed by fracture mechanics principles and thus have an absolute size effect.

INTRODUCTION

Impact remains a problem of importance in composite materials structures because of the possibility of accidental damage. While the general features of impact have been studied by a number of investigators, a number of features still are not well understood. The objective of this paper is to present some new results on dynamic effects in impact, and to present results on size effects in impact damage formation.

In early work, a number of investigators have determined the general susceptibility to impact damage of carbon fiber laminates, and demonstrated the forms of damage that result [1-4]. In further work, attempts were made to analyze the impact event. Sun and co-workers showed how the contact stiffness could be included in the analysis, and made finite element calculations of plate impact [5-7]. Cairns and Lagace [8] presented a technique for getting more detail into the calculation in the vicinity of the impact site. Chang and Kutlu [9] have presented non-linear finite element calculations that included softening of the structure due to delaminations. Scaling of impact has been considered by Morton [10].

The nature of the damage resulting from impact has been discussed by a number of investigators. Boll et al. [11] have given detailed results of micrographs of sections taken from impacted specimens, indicating the widespread microcracking, delaminations, and fiber breakage that can result.

Previous work in our laboratory has involved impact of plates and cylinders in various sizes [12-14]. The experimental program involved five sizes of plates and two sizes of cylinders. Both drop-weight (pendulum) and airgun impacts were employed in order to investigate dynamic effects. Analysis procedures were developed for dynamic impact of plates [12,15]. A feature of the experimental program was the emphasis on scaling with respect to size. Previous reports have detailed the validity of the scaling procedures for structural response as well as the agreement between the analysis and the predicted structural response [12,14]. Determination of damage in the impacted specimens has furnished interesting aspects of damage formation. The aim of the present paper is to present new results on delamination and fiber breakage in impact, and in particular how these forms of damage are affected by dynamic effects and by change of specimen size.

Dynamic analysis procedures were developed for both the plates and the cylinders. In the following some analysis results will be presented that will give insight into dynamic effects, followed by a presentation of some experimental results on dynamic and scaling effects.

DYNAMIC ANALYSES

The calculations shown in this section will use solutions for impact problems of orthotropic plates and cylinders with various boundary conditions. These solution procedures are of two types. The first type is based on Fourier series expansions of the governing variables, combined with Laplace transformation techniques for the structure and impactor dynamics [15,16]. This solution is restricted to simply supported cylinders and plates that are simply supported on all four edges. In addition, the solution requires that the contact indentation law be replaced by a linearized version. The second solution technique is based on a Ritz procedure using beam functions for anisotropic plates with general boundary conditions in conjunction with numerical time integration using the Newmark method [12]. These methods have been compared with experiment [12,14] as well as each other (for plates) and other literature solutions [17].

It is well known that for impacts in which the impactor and target act like a single degree of freedom system with the target behaving as a spring of negligible mass, the target response depends on the energy of impact and not on the specific values of impact mass and velocity. This is the well-known "quasi-static" approximation for impact response. An often employed rule-of-thumb is that the quasi-static approximation is valid if the frequency of the impact is less than 1/3 the lowest natural frequency of the structure [18]. An equivalent rule has been developed that is more convenient to use [19], based on the idea that if the impact mass is large with respect to the structure mass, the impact event can be treated as quasi-static. This idea can be simply related to the conventional rule for the ratio of natural frequencies given above. The approach taken is to develop an expression for an equivalent lumped mass, that can be used in conjunction with the static stiffness to approximate the lowest natural frequency of the structure. To this end we define an equivalent mass implicitly by the following formula.

$$\frac{1}{2}M_{eq}v_c^2 = \frac{1}{2} \int_{Vol} \rho v^2 dVol \quad (1)$$

where M_{eq} is the equivalent lumped mass of the structure, v_c is the peak velocity of the contact point for the impact, v is the peak velocity distribution throughout the impacted structure, and the integral is taken over the entire structure. The above expression is based on equating the energy of the equivalent lumped mass to the energy of the structure. If the assumption is made that the structure is undergoing motion in the mode determined by the quasi-static approximation, then the peak velocities are proportional to the peak displacements, and the peak displacements are those calculated from a static application of load at the contact point. Thus the above can be replaced by

$$\frac{1}{2}M_{eq}\delta_c^2 = \frac{1}{2} \int_{Vol} \rho w^2 dVol \quad (2)$$

where here δ_c is the displacement at the point of impact, and w is the transverse displacement throughout the body as calculated by a static analysis. It is important to note that Eqn 2 enables the equivalent mass to be calculated from a knowledge of the static deformation of the body alone, without requiring access to a dynamic solution. The procedure given in Eqn 2 has been suggested for calculating lumped mass approximations as an approximate method of calculating natural frequencies for beams and rods. Examples of equivalent mass calculations for beams, plates, and cylinders have been given in [19].

Having defined an equivalent lumped mass for the impacted structure, the rule of thumb for the limits of the quasi-static approximation can be reformulated in terms of the ratio of impact mass to equivalent structure mass as follows. The rule of thumb in terms of frequencies is written as

$$\sqrt{\frac{K_{st}}{M_i}} \leq \frac{1}{3} \omega_n \quad (3)$$

If now the lowest natural frequency of the structure is replaced by the approximate relationship

$$\omega_n \approx \sqrt{\frac{K_{st}}{M_{eq}}} \quad (4)$$

then Eqn 3 can be replaced by

$$\sqrt{\frac{K_{st}}{M_i}} \leq \frac{1}{3} \sqrt{\frac{K_{st}}{M_{eq}}} \quad (5)$$

or

$$M_i \geq 9M_{eq} \quad (6)$$

and we have succeeded in recasting a rule of thumb for the limits of the quasi-static approximation for impact problems in terms of the ratio of impact mass to equivalent structure mass.

The rule-of-thumb described above for the limits of the quasi-static approximation can be used to illustrate the dynamic effects that become important as the mass of the impactor is reduced relative to the effective mass of the target. Figures 1 and 2 show typical results of the dynamic calculations for plates and cylinders. The variables shown are peak contact force, peak strain behind the impact point, and peak value of interlaminar shear stress. The specific values differ somewhat, but the trends are the same for all the variables and for both plates and cylinders. In every case these variables increase with respect to the values that would be obtained from the quasi-static analysis at the same impact energy level. Thus the quasi-static analysis is non-conservative for situations in which dynamic effects are important.

EXPERIMENTS

Approximately 400 plate impact and 200 cylinder impact tests have been carried out, using both pendulum and airgun tests. The intent of the airgun tests was to investigate dynamic effects in impact. However the mass ratio's calculated using Eqn 2 above are approximately 4 and 1 for the plates and cylinders, respectively. These values are generally in the "border" region between the quasi-static and dynamic impacts. Although both the experiments and the analyses of the airgun tests reveal dynamic features, the calculations show that peak values of contact force and stress and strain did not differ significantly between the quasi-static (pendulum) and dynamic (airgun) tests.

Experimental evidence for the lack of a significant difference between the quasi-static and dynamic tests was also obtained by comparing the damage produced during the impact. Figures 3 and 4 show delamination extent measured by C-scan after impact for the plates and cylinders respectively. It can be seen that there is little difference between the pendulum and airgun test results, when impact energies are held constant. A reference velocity has been used in these figures, which has an arbitrary value but differs from pendulum to airgun test by a factor of 8, which gives equivalent impact energies as the impact masses differed by a factor of 64.

The specimens were also thermally deformed after impact and attempts were made to quantify the length of regions of broken fibers. The results for two sizes of plates are shown in Fig 5 for both pendulum and airgun experiments. It can be seen again that there is little difference between the pendulum and airgun tests, indicating again that the dynamic effects in the airgun tests are not significant.

One of the major objectives of the experimental program was to develop procedures for extrapolating results from small scale models to larger structures. As has been discussed previously, scaling of the linear structural response seems to be well understood in both the quasi-static and dynamic experiments [12-14]. However the impact damage showed more complex scaling behavior. In particular, it has been shown that delamination shows a direct dependence on the size of the specimen, with larger specimens showing more relative delamination area. This can be explained on the basis of fracture mechanics, which predicts a dependence on the flaw size. Conversely, the broken fiber regions do not show this size dependence. For example, the critical velocity required to just break fibers can be obtained from Fig 5 by extrapolating to zero crack length. It can be seen that this value is essentially the same for the 50x50 and the 200x200 mm plates.

DISCUSSION

The present work seeks to examine dynamic effects in impact tests. Calculations show the importance of dynamic effects in impact, with increased levels of local stress or strain relative to quasi-static impact. However, it is useful to have an a priori estimate of whether dynamic effects will be important in a particular situation. To this end, a "rule-of-thumb" has been developed based on the ratio of impact mass to effective structure mass. This rule of thumb is based entirely on the static solution, and thus does not require knowledge of the dynamic solution. However, if the rule of thumb suggests that dynamic effects will be important, a full dynamic solution is required.

The present experiments on impact of plates and cylinders appear to give results in general agreement with this rule. That is, the rule of thumb indicated that the airgun experiments were still within the range of parameters where the quasi-static solution should be applicable, although at the border of this regime. In fact the experiments showed no significant difference in the damage produced in the pendulum and airgun experiments, both for delamination and for broken fibers.

Scaling of results from small models to larger structures is a matter of much importance in fiber composites, and particularly so for impact loading. The experimental study of scaling revealed a number of interesting conclusions. It was shown that damage formation showed complex scaling behavior. The experimental results show clearly that delamination produced by impact shows a size effect that would be predicted by fracture mechanics. As discussed previously [13,20], the experiments show that larger specimens show more relative delamination, when applied stress levels are held constant. This is an important conclusion in extrapolating impact results. On the other hand, the fiber breakage does not appear to show this effect, with fiber breakage dependent on applied stresses or strains independent of specimen size. This can be seen in the comparison of two plate sizes in Fig 5, and has been discussed further in [20,21].

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Calculation procedures have been developed and carried out for quasi-static and dynamic impact of plates and cylinders. The results show clearly that peak values of contact force and stress and strain near the impact zone have increased values in dynamic impact, so that the quasi-static analysis can underestimate these results. A rule was also developed for estimating the limit of applicability of the quasi-static analysis, based on the ratio of impactor to equivalent target mass. Impact experiments were carried out on plates and cylinders, using both pendulum and airgun apparatus. Although dynamic features were observed in the airgun experiments, the mass ratio indicated that the experiments were on the border between quasi-static and dynamic. The calculation results verified this result, and the experiments showed little difference in damage between the pendulum and airgun tests. Scaling of damage was found to be depend on the type of damage involved.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The contributions of Carl Madsen and Dr. Ralph Nuismer of Hercules Incorporated, Magna, Utah, are gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

1. Starnes, J.H., Rhodes, M.D., and Williams, J.G., "Effect of Impact Damage and Holes on the Compressive Strength of a Graphite/Epoxy Laminate,"

- Nondestructive Evaluation and Flaw Criticality for Composite Materials, ASTM STP 696, pp 145-171 (1979).
2. Labor, J.D., "Impact Damage Effects on the Strength of Advanced Composites," Nondestructive Evaluation and Flaw Criticality for Composite Materials, ASTM STP 696, pp 172-184 (1979).
 3. Williams, J.G., and Rhodes, M.D., "Effect of Resin on Impact Damage Tolerance of Graphite/Epoxy Laminates," Composite Materials: Testing and Design (Sixth Conference), ASTM STP 787, pp 450-480 (1982).
 4. Caprino, G., "Residual Strength Prediction of Impacted CFRP Laminates," J. Composite Materials, 18, pp 508-518 (1984).
 5. Yang, S.H. and Sun, C.T., "Indentation Law for Composite Laminates," Composite Materials: Testing and Design (Sixth Conference), ASTM STP 787, pp 425-449 (1982).
 6. Sun, C.T., and Chen, J.K., "On the Impact of Initially Stressed Composite Laminates," J. Composite Materials., 19, pp 490-504 (1985).
 7. Tan, T.M. and Sun, C.T., "Use of Static Indentation Law in the Impact Analysis of Laminated Composite Plates," J. Composite Materials, 52, pp 6-12 (1985).
 8. Cairns, D.S., and Lagace, P.A., "Thick Composite Plates Subjected to Lateral Loading," J. Applied Mechanics, 54, pp 611-616 (1987).
 9. Chang, F.K., and Kutlu, Z., "Strength and Response of Cylindrical Composite Shells Subjected to Out-of-Plane Loadings," J. Composite Materials, 23, pp 11-31 (1989).
 10. Morton, J., "Scaling of Impact-Loaded Carbon-Fiber Composites," AIAA J., 26, pp 989-994 (1988).
 11. Boll, D.J., Bascom, W.D., Weidner, J.C., and Murri, J.C., "A Microscopy Study of Impact Damage of Epoxy-Matrix Carbon-Fiber Composites," J. Material Sci., 21, pp. 2667 - 2677 (1986).
 12. Qian, Y., and Swanson, S.R., "Experimental Measurement of Impact Response in Carbon/Epoxy Plates," AIAA J, 28, pp 1069-1074 (1990).
 13. Qian, Y., Swanson, S.R., Nuismer, R.J., and Bucinell, R.B., "An Experimental Study of Scaling Rules for Impact Damage in Fiber Composites," J. Composite Materials , 24, pp 559-570 (1990).
 14. Swanson, S.R., Smith, N.L., and Qian, Y., "Analytical and Experimental Strain Response in Impact of Composite Cylinders," Composite Structures, 18, pp 95-108 (1991).
 15. Christoforou, A. P., and Swanson, S. R., "Analysis of Simply-Supported Orthotropic Cylindrical Shells Subject to Lateral Impact Loads," J. Applied Mechanics, 57, pp 376-382 (1990).
 16. Christoforou, A.P., and Swanson, S.R., "Analysis of Impact Response in Composite Plates," Intl. J. Solids and Structures , 27, pp 161-170 (1991).
 17. Qian, Y. and Swanson, S.R., "A Comparison of Solution Techniques for Impact Response of Composite Plates," Composite Structures, 14, pp 177-192 (1990).
 18. Cook, R.D., et al., "Concepts and Applications of Finite Element Analysis," 3d Ed., John Wiley, p 367 (1989).
 19. Swanson, S.R., "Limits of Quasi-Static Solutions in Impact of Composite Structures," Composites Engineering, 2, pp 261-267 (1992).
 20. Swanson, S.R., "On Impact Damage in Fiber Composite Structures," in Damage Mechanics and Localization, AMD Vol 142, MD Vol 34, pp 135-144, Proc. ASME WAM, November 1992.
 21. Swanson, S.R., "Scaling of Impact Damage in Fiber Composites from Laboratory Specimens to Structures," to appear in Composite Structures (1993).

Fig 1. Quasi-static and dynamic response in impact of fiber composite plates. Plates shown are both simply supported and clamped-clamped, free-free. Variables are peak contact force, strain behind the impact point, and interlaminar shear stress, from [19].

Fig 2. Quasi-static and dynamic response in impact of fiber composite cylinders. Cylinders are of two different lengths, differing by a factor of 4. Variables are peak contact force, strain behind the impact point, and interlaminar shear stress, from [19].

Fig 3. Measured delamination size as a function of impact velocity in impact tests of plates. $V_{ref}=24.4$ m/s for airgun, 3.05 m/s for pendulum impact, from [20].

Fig 4. Measured delamination size as a function of impact velocity in impact tests of cylinders. $V_{ref}=61.0$ m/s for airgun, 7.62 m/s for pendulum impact, from [20].

Fig 5. Length of broken fiber region in 50 and 200 mm plates from airgun and pendulum impact. $V_{ref}=24.4$ m/s for airgun, 3.05 m/s for pendulum impact.